

Appendix A: Low-resolution images

In this section, we show images at all the resolution available (i.e., from left to right columns: full resolution, taper=10'', taper=15'' and taper=30'') at each observing frequencies (from top to bottom: uGMRT Band 3, uGMRT Band 4 and MeerKAT) for A3528N (Fig. A.1), A3528S (Fig. A.2) and A3532 (Fig. A.3).

Fig. A.1: Full- (left column) and low-resolution (centre-left, centre-right and right columns) images of A3528N. Top row: uGMRT Band 3; central row: uGMRT Band 4; bottom row: MeerKAT L-band.

A3528S

Fig. A.2: Full- (left column) and low-resolution (centre-left, centre-right and right columns) images of A3528S. Top row: uGMRT Band 3; central row: uGMRT Band 4; bottom row: MeerKAT L-band.

Fig. A.3: Full- (left column) and low-resolution (centre-left, centre-right and right columns) images of A3532. Top row: uGMRT Band 3; central row: uGMRT Band 4; bottom row: MeerKAT L-band.

Appendix B: Surface brightness β -model

In this section, we show the eROSITA images, the assumed β -model and residual maps for A3528 (Fig. B.1) and A3532 (Fig. B.2).

According to the β -model (Cavaliere & Fusco-Femiano 1976), the cluster surface brightness S_X is described as:

$$S_X = S_0 \left[1 + \left(\frac{r}{r_c} \right)^2 \right]^{-3\beta+0.5}, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where r_c is the core radius, and S_0 is the central surface brightness. The β parameter determines the ratio of specific kinetic energies of galaxies and gas (Gitti et al. 2012), and is defined as $\beta = \frac{\sigma_r^2}{k_B T / \mu m_p}$, where σ_r is the line-of-sight velocity dispersion, k_B the Boltzmann parameter, T the ICM temperature, μ the mean molecular weight, and m_p the proton mass.

Fig. B.1: eROSITA count image (left), β -model image (middle), and residual map (right) for A3528. Each of the two sub-clusters (A3528N and A3528S) have been modelled with two different β -models.

Fig. B.2: eROSITA count image (left), β -model image (middle), and residual map (right) for A3532.

Fig. B.3: Comparison of the X-ray surface brightness fluctuations and the radio uGMRT Band 3 emission in A3528S. Red annuli show the two regions, based on the radio emission, where we calculated the X-ray surface brightness residuals. Each black annulus has a width of $\sim 12''$, i.e. the beam size of the radio observations.

Appendix C: Spectral index uncertainty maps

In this section, we present the spectral index uncertainty maps for the clusters in the A3528 cluster complex.

Fig. C.1: Spectral index uncertainty maps for Fig. 6

Fig. C.2: Spectral index uncertainty maps for Fig. 7.

Appendix D: Ha₁₀-FDCA fitting results

In this section, we show the fitting result of the candidate mini-halo in A3528S, using Ha₁₀-FDCA (Boxelaar et al. 2021).

Fig. D.1: Results of the mini-halo fitting (from left to right: radio data, model assumed for the radio emission, residual image). Top panels: uGMRT Band 3. Bottom panels: uGMRT Band 4. The green and red regions in the left and right columns are excluded from the fitting.